

Medicine Traceability System using Blockchain

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ABSTRACT

Prerequisites from purchasers and governments to create increasingly supportable items have expanded amid late years. Regardless of whether items are certified, one can't ensure organizations meet these necessities, since no chain of occasions can check this exists. The transportation business needs certification and data on whether a item is transported economically. In any case, the industry likewise requires follow capacity through the whole production network. In this task, the creators ponder how detectability issues can be tackled from the point of view of a fourth gathering coordinations firm and how the straightforwardness could be expanded. Researchers contend that restricted of comprehending recognizability issues, and in the meantime accomplish straightforwardness, could be to utilize the blockchain technology; an innovation which stores information in sequential request, difficult to control a short time later. Accordingly, the blockchain innovation has been tried on an items now, from stacking at a provider, through a cross-docking terminal and a focal distribution center, to getting at a customers store. By incorporating a blockchain to a web application, empowering examining of QR codes through the camera, and connecting the data from the QR code to the blockchain, computerized impressions between the gatherings could be made at each transaction. The data on the blockchain empowers organizations to fortify the relationships with current clients and to pull in new ones

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1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this system is to contribute to two different areas. Firstly, the field of tracking and tracing of goods, primarily in the medical industry. This by exploring how block chain technology could be applicable in the distribution part of a supply chain. Due to the increased demand of transparency from different stakeholders, our second intention of the study is to suggest a tool for managing transparency in the field of logistics by using blockchain technology. The purpose of the system is to study the real-world problem i.e. the traceability issues for the

cooperative fourth party logistic (4PL) company. The company has a mismatch of the physical and digital flow, and the research intend to study if the

1.2 Motivation

The purpose of the system is to study and overcome the real world problem occurs in medicine supply chain and presence of counterfeit drugs and medicine. Provide the transparency to end user..

2. Literature Survey

In this section we will see the various studies and research conducted in order to identify the current scenarios and trends in digital learning and also the attempts of introducing block chain concept in education

2.1 Main Contributions

The supply chain network consists of various parties; suppliers, intermediates, third party provision (3PL), fourth party provision (4PL) and customers (Mehmann & Teuteberg, 2016). A 4PL could be a non-asset primarily based measuring device World Health Organization manage clients' offer chains to form business worth (Win, 2008). additional actors inside the chain produce immense and complicated offer chains. One a part of the quality is that the truck transportation, that is that the most typical used approach of transports (Caputo, Fratocchi, & Pelagage, 2006). The transport trade consists of hauliers from whom a empor bought the transport service, World Health Organization successively will use subcontractors to accomplish the transport (Sternberg, Germann, & Klaas-Wissing, 2013). The subcontractors may use extra subcontractors, leading to multiple layers and ends up in difficulties in terms of dominant the transport section and its parties. it's to those lower layers that corporations ought to provide their full attention, since the pertaining parties usually expertise unhealthy and unhealthy operating conditions at the side of low salaries (Svensson, 2009), that causes unsustainability within the trade.

The property awareness, not solely from social aspects however conjointly environmental, has fully grown throughout the last decade to become a very important a part of offer chain management (Gualandris, Klassen, Vachon, & Kalchschmidt, 2015). a mixture of pressure from government and therefore the public, forces corporations to enhance their property practices (Sarkis, Zhu, & Lai, 2011). Nowadays, stakeholders interest in what a firm waste terms of property practices (Gonzalez-Benito, Lannelongue, & Queiruga, 2011; Gray, 2013) and shoppers demand additional property and clear product (Trienekens, Wognum, Beulens, & van der Vorst, 2012). info concerning environmental and social performance of suppliers and its product is typically accessible through completely different certifications (Gualandris et al., 2015), honest trade as an example, however there's no info or certification on however the transportation of AN eco-friendly product is dead (Sternberg, 2016).

Regulations is a method to figure proactively for a property trade, however traceability may have an effect on the property (Egels-Zanden, Hulthen, & Wulff, 2015). In terms of traceability, all style of food ought to be traceable through all stages of production, process and distribution, wherever every party square measure answerable for tracing the food one step back and one leap forward (European Parliament, 2002). This to secure that the entire history will be renovated if required, that is particularly necessary if the food is contaminated. A traceability system should support each pursuit and tracing, wherever pursuit is employed to stay record of the merchandise at every stage, and tracing is that the method to spot the origin of a product, i.e. reconstructing the history of the information recorded by the pursuit method (Pizzuti & Mirabelli, 2015). By implementing an appropriate traceability system, an organization might acquire higher management of the

provision chain and just in case of contaminated food, the speed of detection it may well be improved (Pizzuti & Mirabelli, 2015).

Related to traceability is transparency, since it for a provision firm is that the track and trace services that permit higher degree of visibility (Hultman & Axelsson, 2007). Doorey (2011) and mole (2015) outline transparency as revelation of knowledge. Besides the data sharing inside the provision chain, there's AN accumulated demand for transparency by different stakeholders, like shoppers and government (Carter & Rogers, 2008; Doorey, 2011). The potential advantages with being clear is that it will produce business opportunities (Svensson, 2009), improve (Carter & Rogers, 2008) and cause a good name (Fombrun, 1996) for the firm. Another necessary side of transparency is that the info imbalance. the data imbalance makes it not possible to decide on the merchandise that's believed to yield bigger worth (Wognum, Bremmers, Trienekens, van der Vorst, & Bloemhof, 2011). Further, in terms of company Social Responsibility (CSR), it's crucial to implement transparency so as to get a CSR policy that's property, since an organization that perform well in CSR cannot distinguish oneself from different competitors while not transparency (Dubink, Graafland, & van Liedekerke, 2008).

One technology that has been given a lot of attention throughout the previous couple of years, which may provide each traceability and transparency, is that the blockchain technology (YliHuumo, Ko, Choi, Park, & Smolander, 2016). A technology that originally was made-up to support the digital currency of Bitcoin (Nakamoto, 2008). The blockchain technology stores information in blocks, in written record order, and because of a mathematical trapdoor (Brennan & Lunn, 2016), the information keep within the blocks is not possible to change or take away (Nakamoto, 2008; Fanning & Centers, 2016). Copies of the chain of blocks, thence the term blockchain, and thereby the data, square measure distributed among the participants within the network (Tsai, Blower, Zhu, Yu, & Ieee, 2016). The copies of the blockchain square measure then updated once a replacement block of knowledge is other to the chain (Swan, 2015). So far, analysis on blockchains has primarily been centered on digital currencies, and specifically Bitcoin (Yli-Huumo et al., 2016), however the blockchain technology isn't absolutely explored (Lemieux, 2016) and it's same to be of future potential (Hull et al., 2016); particularly as a recordkeeping technology (Lemieux, 2016). The irreversible information storing technology that blockchain permits has created the trade of food offer chain a remarkable application space (Tian, 2016), wherever the technology might support traceability, and thereby achieving transparency (Hancock & Vaizey, 2016).

To ensure that the study has high believability, Björklund and Paulsson (2014) and rule (2009) describes the importance of validity and dependability. Validity implies to live what the study extremely desires to live (Björklund & Paulsson, 2014). rule (2009) states that validity will be divided into 2 differing kinds, internal and external, wherever the primary one is unsuitable for alpha studies. External validity is a very important a part of an instructional thesis and can't be excluded (Björklund & Paulsson, 2014), and therefore the target is to analyze if the findings may well be generalized (Yin, 2009; Björklund & Paulsson, 2014). So, to form positive that no info would

travel by disregarded and guarantee internal control throughout the case study, recordings and transcriptions were fabricated from all interviews and observations. once the case study observations and therefore the interviews, a transcript was created and reconnected with the concerned ones, either by e-mail, phone or each. By doing that the respondent has the chance to purpose on misunderstandings and thereby strengthen the validity. To strengthen the external validity, a field trial with the developed physical object, that was supported blockchain technology, was dead on the studied flow.

Reliability will be achieved by documenting the various procedures in such the way that that a later investigator might repeat the study everywhere once more and arrive to constant findings and conclusions (Yin, 2009). to make sure dependability the authors created AN in-depth documentation information wherever all information collected from the whole thesis were control. The in-depth information may well be generalized as a tree structure with folders, wherever the content was divided into additional folders then forth. Despite the fact that one case study was used, similar results might are have achieved by mistreatment another 4PL company. This, since the studied 4PL company complies with the definition of a 4PL company.

A way to extend each dependability and validity is to use triangulation that primarily implies that the studied object

ought to be approached from completely different directions (Van Delaware Ven, 2007; Yin, 2009; Björklund & Paulsson, 2014). Within the study, the matter has been approached by doing a comprehensive literature review, followed up by observations and interviews from completely different actors within the studied flow. Lastly, and most significantly, a field trial was performed. the sphere check gave the authors insights from the surroundings wherever the physical object may well be employed in the longer term. These insights were then compared with the results from previous studies.

3. Implementation

3.1 System Architecture

- Request sent : A request to append a transaction to supply chain is sent.
- Request validated: A block is created after every component of a transaction is completed and validated using proven, trusted algorithm. A verified transaction can contain data events and smart contracts.
- Block created: Blocks can be data or can include smart contracts autonomously trigger other transaction when reached milestone are reached or completed.
- Append: Once you put data on blockchain it can be there forever. It can never be removed or altered by any party or user.

Fig:-System architecture

3.2 Working

Web based portal enables Admin to add Company details and view list of Company, Distributor, Dealer, Medical Stores under the company. Similarly, Com-pany can add Distributors to which they are distributing the medicines and also view dealers and medical stores of the Distributor. This is a hierarchy structure of which admin is on the top of the hierarchy structure and Medical store is on the bottom of this hierarchy. This web portal also enables Medical store to view the stock of the medicines available with him according to which store person can buy new stocks from the dealer.

Android app enables the scanning of the QR codes printed on each medicine packets. Company on manufacturing scans the Medicine thus creating Block 0, in the database. On further scanning of the medicines each block is added in the chain. App has individual logins for Company, Distributor, Dealer, Medical store and User. Database is distributed on multiple systems and when a transaction takes place authenticity is verified my multiple systems and a common consensus is reached upon.

3.3 Snapshot

Fig:-login page

Fig:-Blockchain Panel

4. Advantages and Disadvantages

4.1 Advantages

- The manufacturing supply chain – a logistics nightmare
- Drug safety – how drugs are manufactured
- Inventory management
- Public safety and consumer awareness
- Clinical trial management.

5. Conclusion

Blockchain is an attractive solution to supporting supply chain. Much like the Internet and search engines have provided a way to search and acquire data that resides in many places, blockchain promises to do the same in a secure environment for business transactions and consumer and patient interactions.

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